

Presentation of Decreased Bone Mineral Density in a Woman Diagnosed with Familial Mediterranean Fever: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Background/Objective: Familial Mediterranean fever (FMF) is an inherited autoinflammatory condition caused by mutations in the MEFV gene characterized by recurrent self-limited febrile episodes and polyserositis. Patients with familial Mediterranean fever are found to have low bone mineral density with elevated bone markers, such as serum osteoprotegerin (OPG). Its incidence is estimated to be high in the Turkish population at 1/3500. As this clinical entity is rare, it often remains underdiagnosed and underreported. There is scant evidence from a few studies in the literature.

We aim to depict in our case the significance of early osteoporosis screening interventions in FMF patients to mitigate the future risk of fractures.

Case Presentation: We report a case of a 45-year-old female with Familial Mediterranean Fever (FMF) on colchicine therapy who presented to an outpatient endocrinology clinic for evaluation. Her past medical history was significant for hypothyroidism, vitamin D deficiency, malabsorption, obesity (status post gastric sleeve surgery), IgA nephropathy, nephrolithiasis, and osteopenia. She was found to have reduced bone mineral density with a T-score of -3.7 in the lumbar spine, and T-score of -2.8 in the femoral neck on a recent DEXA scan.

Conclusion: Regular screening for osteoporosis in patients with familial Mediterranean fever with DEXA scan is recommended. While it has been reported that significantly elevated serum OPG concentration in FMF is a protective mechanism that prevents bone loss, chronic inflammatory activity and malabsorption may contribute to bone loss. This case acts as a cautionary reminder of the diagnostic and therapeutic challenges associated with FMF and identifying risk factors to prevent further bone loss.

Keywords: Osteoporosis; Familial Mediterranean fever; Bone mineral density; Serum bone marker levels

CASE REPORT

History of Presenting Illness:

A 45-year-old woman with a past medical history of familial Mediterranean fever (FMF), hypothyroidism, gastric sleeve surgery 10 years prior (with 50% of decrease in body weight), malabsorption, vitamin D deficiency, and IgA nephropathy, presented to our outpatient endocrinology clinic for evaluation of hypothyroidism and bone loss. She reported that her family history was significant for FMF in her sister and cousins. She described easy fatigability, alternating cold and heat intolerance, neck pain, diarrhea, headache, insomnia, and decreased concentration. Due to a recent stress, a flare of FMF had just occurred. She denied fever, chills, dyspnea, palpitations, muscle weakness, recent falls and fractures. Her physical activity is limited due to FMF. She had never smoked and reported occasional alcohol consumption. Current medications included colchicine 1.8 mg daily and levothyroxine 75 mcg daily. Vitamins included iron, vitamin D3, and a multivitamin. Physical examination was notable for BMI of 20 and diffusely thinned hair. No musculoskeletal deformities were present. Laboratory testing revealed adequate replacement with levothyroxine and vitamin D. Bone density performed by DEXA revealed decreased bone mineral density with T-scores of -3.7 in the lumbar spine and -2.8 in the right femoral neck.

DISCUSSION

Familial Mediterranean fever (FMF) is an inherited (autosomal recessive) autoinflammatory condition characterized by recurrent self-limited febrile episodes and polyserositis that is caused by mutations in the MEFV gene on the short arm of chromosome 16.[1,8] The MEFV gene encodes the protein pyrin/ marenostin, which plays an important role in inflammation and apoptosis.[2,8] FMF is common in Jewish, Turkish and Arab populations.[7] The second most common manifestation of FMF following abdominal pain is rheumatological.[8] Colchicine is proven to be effective in preventing FMF flares in more than 60% of patients. Anti-interleukin-1 biological therapy helps in colchicine-resistant therapy.[13,14] Several proinflammatory cytokines such as TNF-alpha, interleukin IL-1, IL-6, IL-11, IL-15 and IL-17 influence osteoclast differentiation, leading to the bone resorption that is responsible for the decreased BMD in FMF.[5] Along with inflammation occurring during acute flares, it has been proven that subclinical inflammation occurs between attacks.[3,4] Studies have shown that T scores and Z scores of the lumbar spine and femoral neck are significantly lower in the FMF group in comparison with the healthy population.[2,10,11] Patients who show high levels of osteoprotegerin (OPG) have a low risk of osteoporosis. OPG is a glycoprotein that acts as a decoy receptor for the receptor activator of nuclear factor kappa-B ligand (RANKL) which inhibits osteoclastogenesis.[15] Higher levels of OPG are found in patients with in RA, IBD and FMF, which may be a response to inflammation, further preventing bone loss as a compensatory mechanism.[2] In our case, the patient has reduced BMD which may be due to the underlying pathophysiology of FMF.

Variants of systemic amyloidosis, commonly the nephropathic type, have been portrayed predominantly in patients with familial Mediterranean fever. However, intestinal amyloidosis is one of the complications rarely discussed in literature. Amyloid deposition in the GI tract causes malabsorption of vitamin D and calcium. Studies

showed low levels of vitamin D levels in FMF patients. As described by Ravid et al, minor abnormalities of vitamin B12 and iron absorption were also found in a few patients due to parenchymal deposits in mucosa of GI tract.[16] These factors contribute to the diminished effects of OPG in FMF patients.

We presume that, while our patient may have higher levels of OPG as a compensatory mechanism to reduce the risk of fragility fractures, the addition of malabsorption and consequently vitamin D deficiency to her chronic inflammation contributed to her bone loss. Chronic ongoing inflammation in FMF is the main culprit of decreased BMD in this population. Early bone density testing is recommended in patients with FMF to prevent the risk of progression of osteoporosis and initiate appropriate treatment to mitigate its pathologic course.

CONCLUSION

Regular screening for osteoporosis using DEXA in patients with familial Mediterranean fever should be considered. It has been reported that significantly elevated serum OPG concentration in FMF is a protective mechanism that prevents bone loss, but chronic ongoing inflammatory activity and malabsorption may overwhelm this mechanism and lead to osteoporosis in FMF. This case acts as a cautionary reminder of the diagnostic and therapeutic challenges associated with identifying risk factors to prevent bone loss and initiate appropriate treatment for early onset osteoporosis in patients with FMF.

INFORMED CONSENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient prior to the drafting of the manuscript.

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